

TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT AND ITS IMPACT ON EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE -A CONCEPTUAL STUDY

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Abstract :

Employees are the major assets of any organization. Every organization needs well trained employees to perform the activities effectively and efficiently. It is the continuous process of the organizations that helps to develop skills, knowledge, and abilities. Training and development lead to better performance of employees. The success of the organizations depends on employee performance. In this globalization era, training is crucial for the competent and challenging business. It is the nerve that needs to help enhancing the quality of work life of employees and development the organization. Training and development are the crucial factors of enlightening the employee performance in most organizations. The purpose of the study is to find out the impact of training and development on employee performance. With suitable training and development opportunities, as well as effective employee performance assessment approaches, employees will be capable of assisting the organization in achieving its competitive posture in today's global market.

Key words: *Employee Performance, Employee Productivity, Organization Goals, and Performance Measure*

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Introduction :

Effective training and development is an investment in the human resources of an organization, with both immediate and long-range returns. Training is a key element for improved performance; it can enlarge the level of individual and organizational competency. Training holds the key to unlock the potential growth and development opportunities to achieve a competitive edge. Training programs helps in making acquaintance of employees with more advance technology and attaining robust competencies and skills in order to handle the functions and basics of newly introduced technical equipment. Training facilitates the updating of skills and lead to increase commitment, well - being, and sense of belonging, thus directly strengthening the organization's competitiveness (Acton and Golden, 2002; Karia and Ah-mad, 2000; Karia, 1999). Training has the distinct role in the achievement of an organizational goal by

incorporating the interests of organization and the workforce (Stone R J. Human Resource Management, 2002). There is no doubt that training is important in all aspect for an organization. Now a day's training is the most important factor in the business world because training increases the efficiency and the effectiveness of both employees and the organization. Training is important to enhance the capabilities of employees. Recent researches reveal that training enables most organizations meet their goals and objectives. In doing so employees are able to learn new work concepts, refresh their skills, improve their work attitude and boost productivity (Cole 2002).

Objective of the Study :

To know the Training and Development and its impact on employee performance

Research Methodology :

The research paper is an attempt of exploratory research, based on the secondary data sourced from various journals.

Employee Training and Development :

Organizations aspire to be successful through differentiated programs, services, capabilities, and products. However, such elements need to be envisioned, developed, implemented, and sustained by well-trained individuals. According to Feldman (as cited by Jehanzeb & Bashir, 2013), Training and development requires emotional agreement, meaning that the organization and individuals will partner in achieving long-term commitment through career advancement and training opportunities. But, what is training and development? What is it for? What approaches can be used? What are its benefits? How can leaders support this effort?

Training and Development Conceptualized :

Training and development is a function within Human Resources management used to fulfill the gaps between current and expected performance (Elnaga& Imran, 2013; Nassazi, 2013). According to Business Dictionary (training, n.d.), training is an "organized activity aimed at imparting information and/or instructions to improve the recipient's performance or to help him or her attain a required level of knowledge or skill." Training is planned and systematic activities which are focused on enhancing the level of skills, knowledge, and competency (Nassazi, 2013).

Benefits of Training and Development :

Employee training and development is one of the most significant motivators used to help both individuals and organizations in achieving their short-term and long-term goals and objectives. Training and development not only enhance knowledge, skills, and attitudes, but it also offers several other benefits. The following are common benefits of employee training and development, according to Nassazi (2013): (1) It increases employees' morale, confidence, and motivations. (2) It lowers production costs because individuals are able to reduce waste. (3) It promotes a sense of security which in turn reduces turnover and absenteeism. (4) It increases employees' involvement in the change process by providing the competencies necessary to adjust to new and challenging situations. (5) It opens

the doors for recognition, higher pay, and promotion. (6) It helps the organization in improving the availability and quality of its staff. It is noteworthy to remember that individuals become more productive (Bapna, Langer, Mehra, Gopal, & Gupta, 2013), because training and development programs improve individuals' skills and abilities. Even organizations offer tuition reimbursement for individuals to attend such programs (Jehanzeb& Bashir, 2013).

Employee Performance :

The training and development function is mainly responsible for employee performance (Asim, 2013). Performance can be demonstrated in the improvement of production, easiness in utilizing new technology, or being a highly motivated individual (Nassazi, 2013). As organizational leaders strive to achieve higher levels of employee performance, they should establish goals and standards, which performance can be measured against.

Employee Performance Conceptualized :

Employee performance is defined as the outcome of individuals with respect to process, results, relevance, and success (Nassazi, 2013). According to Arinanye (2015), the measures of success are focused on productivity, efficiency, effectiveness, quality, and attendance of work. It is the overall achievement of a particular task measured against pre-selected standards of accuracy, cost, and speed; or the strategic approach to enhancing organizational effectiveness by improving the performance of individuals who work in the organization.

Employee Performance Evaluation :

There are organizations that may not be using a systematic approach for assessing employee performance. Therefore, the concern of this action is that it produces unclear, inefficient, and ambiguous evaluation results (Ahmed, Sultana, Paul, & Azeem, 2013). For this reason, it is vital for organizations to create a systematic approach for assessing performance. Typically, employee performance is measured in terms of outcomes and behaviors, according to predetermined standards set by the organization. Employee performance outcomes may be determined on personal, organizational, environmental, motivation, skill level aptitudes, or role perceptions factors. Nassazi (2013) and Arinanye (2015) provided four examples of employee performance assessment metrics used in organizations: (1) Productivity which is the amount of input resources converted into goods and services. (2) Efficiency and effectiveness which is the capacity of producing outcomes with minimal resources in order to achieve particular objectives. (3) Quality which is a distinctive trait of a product or service that fulfils a need. (4) Profitability which is the capability to consistently earn profit during a time period.

Employee Performance Evaluation Conceptualized :

Employee performance evaluation is an important element in enhancing the quality of work (Shaout& Yousif, 2014). It is one of the most applied techniques organizational leaders use in the workplace (Long, Kowang, Ismail, & Rasid, 2013). According to Kirovska and Qoku (2014), it is a formal, structured system of assessing the characteristics of employee behavior in regards to outcomes. It is a process that examines particular performance

objectives over a period of time. Commonly, organizational leaders assess employee performance quarterly or annually (Shaout& Yousif, 2014). Nassazi (2013) mentioned that the frequency is usually determined based on resource capability and objectives to be assessed. Such objectives may be categorized as developmental or administrative. The developmental objectives are focused on providing feedback, recognizing strengths and weaknesses, identifying goals, classifying training needs, improving communication, and providing time for employees to voice their concerns. The administrative objectives are mostly focused on documenting decisions, identifying high potential employees, determining new assignments and transfers, recognizing poor performance, deciding on layoffs, validating employee selection criteria, and achieving legal standards and requirements.

Generally, employee performance evaluation requires the supervisor to have a conversation with the employee, and then completing a form or systems to track the conversation, needs, and action plan. An effective employee performance evaluation session helps organizational leaders in making the right decisions for the employee's success and development (Long, Kowang, Ismail, & Rasid, 2013). In addition, the overall perspective of employee performance evaluation is centralized on recognizing the current skills' status of the workforce. Such a status requires the collection of diverse accurate and unbiased data in order to assess the employees' contribution to the organization (Shaout& Yousif, 2014) and to make organizational and personnel decisions (Ahmed, Sultana, Paul, & Azeem, 2013). Knowing the use of employee performance evaluation data may assist leaders in stimulating, motivating, and directing team members. The higher the motivation of team members are, the greater results the team and organization attain (Kirovska&Qoku, 2014).

Employee Evaluation Methods

Shaout and Yousif (2014, pp. 966-967) provided 10 examples of traditional and more contemporary methods for evaluating employee performance:

1. Ranking Method: Organizational leaders rank employees according to merit from best to worst.
2. Graphic Rating Scales: This method lists several traits and a range of performance for each trait; then, employees are graded by aligning the score that best describes their level of performance for each trait.
3. Critical Incident Method: Leaders keep a record of unusual behaviors and revisit it with the employees in order to find the resources that will help improve their performance.
4. Narrative Essay: Leaders write an explanation of employee's strengths and weaknesses based on overall impressions of performance, capabilities, and qualifications with recommendations necessary for improving performance.
5. Management by Objectives: Leaders grade performance based on formulated objectives, execution process, and constructive feedback. This systematic approach consists of strategic planning, objectives hierarchy, objectives setting, action planning, method implementation, control and appraisal, as well as subsystems, organizational, and management development.

6. Behaviorally Anchored Rating Scales: This method helps leaders in contrasting employee performance against particular behaviors by using numerical ratings and behavioral statements that describe each element of performance.
7. Humans Resource Accounting: Leaders assess employee performance based on human resource costing and accounting, as well as its contribution to the organization.
8. Assessment Centre: This approach requires leaders to participate in work-related exercises, work groups, computer simulations, fact finding exercises, analysis/decision making problems, role playing, and oral presentation activities in order to be assessed by trained observers.
9. 360 Degree: This approach assesses the influence of actions based on feedback provided by diverse individuals, such as the immediate supervisor, team members, customers, peers, and self.
10. 720 Degree: This method allows external sources, such as stakeholders, family members, suppliers, and communities to provide their feedback about an organization, leaders, and individuals.

Reasons and Ways for Handling Performance Evaluation Failures :

Organizational leaders should keep in mind the reasons why employee performance evaluation fails. Nassazi (2013) provided several reasons, for examples: Lack of information, lack of evaluation skills, not taking evaluation seriously, not being prepared, not being honest and sincere, ineffective discussion with employees, unclear language, and insufficient reward for performance. In addition, F. Nichols (as cited by Long, Kowang, Ismail, & Rasid, 2013) stated there are additional concerns perceived by organizational leaders in regards to employee performance evaluations; for examples, (1) employees set easily attainable goals, (2) creation of negative emotions and feelings, (3) no collaboration and teamwork opportunities, (4) importance on tasks rather than results, (5) promotion of short-term views and organizational politics, and (6) expensive practices for conducting and handling performance evaluations problems and appeals.

Through performance evaluations, leaders are able to identify whether employees have accomplished the work tasks in an effective manner and recognize the challenges employees have experienced during the performance on such activities. Leaders should not make employees behave like the leaders; instead, leaders should recognize that employees have their own values, morals, virtues, and faults. Such factors should be utilized in the best possible way in order to improve performance, while attaining organizational goals. If performance is unacceptable, leaders are required to provide additional support in order to enhance employee performance through coaching, mentoring, counselling, or any other approach (Kirovska & Qoku, 2014).

Evaluating employee performance is not an easy task, since it may impact all dimensions of employees' perceptions and reactions. However, it provides a holistic view regarding the employees' current state of performance. Based on such an outlook, leaders should find diverse ways to not only improve performance, but also to achieve predetermined organizational standards. For many leaders, failure is not an option; however, it is their responsibility to support team members in their journey to become successful professionals, individuals who can effectively perform their job, while achieving organizational goals and objectives.

Conclusion :

Employees are the most valuable asset of the organization as they take responsibility for enhanced customer satisfaction and quality of products and services. Without proper training and development opportunities, they would not be able to accomplish their tasks at their full potential. Employees who are fully capable to perform their job-related tasks tend to keep their jobs longer due to higher job satisfaction. Training and development is a vital tool used to not only maximize the performance of employees, but also to help them in becoming more efficient, productive, satisfied, motivated, and innovative in the workplace (Elnaga& Imran, 2013). Identifying the right learning opportunities for employees will help the organization in achieving its competitive posture in today's global market.

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